

Title: THE RESILIENT FAMILY AS AN AUTOPOIETIC SYSTEM

Author: Walter M. Fontanini

Affiliation: Semmelweis University

Contact: fontanini.walter@phd.semmelweis.hu

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Abstract

This perspective article explores the family as an autopoietic and homeostatic system, a concept derived from Maturana and Varela's theory of self-producing and self-maintaining systems.

Traditionally viewed in sociology as a duocentric system or a dyadic society, the family is a basic socio-dynamic unit essential for socialisation, emotional nurturing and identity formation. The duocentric nature of the family emphasises its central role in intimate, reciprocal relationships, typically between partners, parents, and children. In addition, the family functions as a socio-dynamic unit, constantly adapting to internal and external changes and demonstrating resilience in the face of adversity.

However, this article advances a new hypothesis that the concept of autopoiesis, complemented by homeostasis - which refers to the family's efforts to maintain stability and equilibrium through adaptive mechanisms - provides a framework for better understanding the family's capacity for self-regulation. This approach emphasises the family's ability to generate and sustain itself through internal interactions and processes such as communication patterns, role distribution and emotional regulation.

These principles have significant implications for family therapy, shifting the focus from external interventions to enhancing the family's intrinsic self-regulatory capacities. Indeed, therapists aim to facilitate the family's internal patterns of communication and interaction,

empowering them to address and resolve issues autonomously, in full accordance with the concept of homeostasis.

This philosophical approach underlines the importance of fostering resilience within families, promoting their ability to reorganise themselves and thrive amid challenges.

In conclusion, recognising the family as an autopoietic system enriches sociological and therapeutic perspectives by highlighting the essential role of internal family dynamics in ensuring stability and well-being in contemporary life.

Keywords: Autopoiesis, homeostasis, family, resilience, self-regulation, family therapy